

Meta Substituted Aromatic Amines As Corrosion Inhibitors For 70/30 Brass In Nitric Acid

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NITRIC acid is highly corrosive to copper and copper-zinc alloys. The corrosive attack of nitric acid on copper is mainly due to the nitrous acid formed during the reaction between copper and nitric acid. Therefore a substance which prevents the autocatalytic cycle of the formation of nitrous acid would act as a corrosion inhibitor. As aromatic amines can react with nitrous acid they should be able to retard the corrosion of copper and copper-zinc alloys in nitric acid. Orthosubstituted aromatic amines have been previously investigated as corrosion inhibitors for 70/30 brass in nitric acid¹. The present article reports the use of *m*-toluidine, *m*-anisidine, *m*-chloroaniline and *m*-nitroaniline as corrosion inhibitors for 70/30 brass in nitric acid solution.

Experimental

70/30 brass supplied by Messrs. Kamani Metals Bombay, was used for the study. The preparation of specimens and corrosion tests were carried out as described in earlier publication². The change in potential with time of 70/30 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors is given in Fig-1. The effect of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 2.0N nitric acid is given in Fig-2. All potential values are with reference to saturated calomel electrode.

Figure 1 : Change in potential of 70/30 brass with time in 2.0N nitric acid in the presence and absence of inhibitors

- △—△ m nitroaniline
- m chloroaniline
- ×—× m toluidine
- m anisidine
- uninhibited 2.0N nitric acid

Figure 2 : Influence of current density on the cathode and anode potentials of 70/30 brass in 2.0N nitric acid in presence and absence of inhibitors

- m nitroaniline
- △—△ m chloroaniline
- ×—× m toluidine
- △—△ m anisidine
- uninhibited 2.0N nitric acid

***m*-toluidine :** In the concentration range 8.70-43.5 ml/l, *m*-toluidine affords 92% protection to 70/30 brass in 2-4N HNO₃. In the presence of meta toluidine, the potential values with time are negative than those in its absence indicating the action of the inhibitors on the local cathodes. Meta toluidine induces a significant increase in the cathode polarisation. At the current density of 8.12x10⁻⁴ amp/cm² the shift in cathode potentials during cathode polarisation in the presence of meta toluidine is 675 mv, the corresponding shift in its absence is only 9 mv. *m*-toluidine increases the anode polarisation to a certain extent.

***m*-anisidine :** Even at 4.35 ml/l concentration *m*-anisidine give 98-99% protection 70/30 brass in 3-4N HNO₃. A comparison of the results obtained with *m*-toluidine and *m*-anisidine shows the better inhibitive action of *m*-anisidine. In the presence of *m*-anisidine, the potential values with time are negative than those in its absence indicating its action on the local cathodes. Addition of meta anisidine induces a significant increase in the cathode polarisation only after the current density 1.62 x 10⁻³ amp/cm². In the current density range 1.62 x 10⁻⁶-8.12x10⁻⁴ amp/cm² the shifts in anode potentials during anode polarisation are more than the corresponding shifts in the anode potentials during anode polarisation. Subsequently, however, the increase in the anode polarisation is to a lesser extent.

***m*-chloroaniline :** meta chloroaniline is a very good inhibitor for the corrosion of 70/30 brass in nitric acid solutions. The effective concentration range of *m*-chloroaniline is 2.17-8.70ml/l (99% protection in 2-4N HNO₃). In the presence of metachloroaniline, the potential values with time are negative throughout indicating its action on the local cathodes. Metachloroaniline induces a considerable increase in the cathode polarisation and the anode polarisation is increased to a certain extent.

***m*-nitroaniline :** *m*-nitroaniline is a satisfactory inhibitor at 0.2% concentration. For 15 min duration, the actual loss in weight of 70/30 brass decreases as the

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concentration of HNO_3 increases. It is interesting to note that for 15 and 30 min durations, in the presence of 0.2% meta nitroaniline, the loss in weight of 70/30 brass in 3.0N nitric acid is slightly less than that in 2.0N nitric acid. In the presence of meta nitroaniline the potential values with time are more negative than those in its absence indicating its action on the local cathodes. Addition of meta nitroaniline induces a significant increase in the cathode polarisation.

Conclusions: All the substances are satisfactory inhibitors for the corrosion of 70/30 brass in the nitric acid. The order of efficiency is m-nitroaniline > m-chloroaniline > m-anisidine > m-toluidine.

References

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Interaction of Yttrium(III), Lanthanum(III), Cerium(III) and Uranium(VI) with Salicyloyl-hydrazide.

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THE chelating behaviour of salicyloyl-hydrazide with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} , has been reported by Jabalpurwala and co-workers¹. The present paper describes the results of potentiometric titration studies on Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} chelates of salicyloyl-hydrazide in water dioxane mixture at ionic strengths of 0.01, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15M.

Experimental

Salicyloyl-hydrazide was prepared by the known method². Due to the limited solubility of the ligand in water, pH titration studies were carried out in 50% water dioxane mixture. In the case of Ce^{3+} , 25:75 water-dioxane mixture was used due to precipitation in 50% water dioxane mixture. Solutions of potassium nitrate and nitric acid were used to maintain the ionic strengths. The titrations were carried out at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using Calvin-Bjerrum^{3,4} technique as used by Irving and Rossotti⁵. The following solutions (total volumes 20 ml in each case) were titrated against standard KOH solution; A) (2 ml of 0.01M HNO_3 ; B) (A + 2 ml of 0.05M ligand; C) B + 2 ml of 0.01M metal ion. Since the pH titrations were carried out in water dioxane medium, appropriate corrections as per Van Uitert and Hass⁶ was applied.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\log K_1^H$ at the various ionic concentrations are reported in Table 1. The formation curves (Fig. 1.) extend between $\bar{n}=0$ and $\bar{n}=3$ for La^{3+} , Y^{3+}

FIG. 1 FORMATION CURVES OF SALICYLOYLHYDRAZIDE CHELATES

chelates and $\bar{n}=0$ and $\bar{n}=2$ in the case of UO_2^{2+} and Ce^{3+} chelates. It is observed that UO_2^{2+} forms chelates of 1:2 composition in the pH range 3.20-6.25, while the same stoichiometry is obtained for Ce^{3+} chelates in the pH range 5.00-7.50. It has also been observed that La^{3+} and Y^{3+} form three types of chelates in the ratio of 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 in the pH range 6.00-8.75 and 5.00-8.00 respectively.

The values of stability constants were obtained by interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values⁷. The values of $\log K_2$ and overall stability constants, $\log \beta_2$ of 1:2 chelates of UO_2^{2+} , were obtained from Fig. 1, using the following relations.

$$\log K_2 = (\text{pL})\bar{n} = 1.5$$

$$\log \beta_2 = 2(\text{pL})\bar{n} = 1.0$$

The formation curve for UO_2^{2+} system starts at the value above $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and, therefore, the $\log K_1$ values for this system were obtained as difference.

$$\log K_1 = \log \beta_2 - \log K_2.$$

The metal-ligand stability data at various μ values (Table 1.) reveal that values of $\log K_1/K_2$ and $\log K_2/K_3$ are positive and $\log \beta_2$ values suggest that with an increase in the ionic strength of the medium the values of stability constants of La^{3+} , Y^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} chelates with salicyloyl-hydrazide decrease. According to Huckel⁸ the activity of the metal ion for its interaction with other molecular species varies inversely as the ionic strength of the medium in which the reactions were studied. On this basis, the decrease in stabilities for salicyloyl-hydrazide chelates of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} in solutions of increasing ionic strength is justified which is also in agreement with the results obtained by the authors⁹ for La^{3+} complexes.

The observed stability order $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Y}^{3+} > \text{La}^{3+}$ for $\log \beta_n$ values is justified on the basis of Z^2/r values for these metal ions which are in the sequence given above. The $\log \beta_n$ values for cerium complexes are less as compared with those of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} and UO_2^{2+} ions. Since in the case of Ce^{3+} , the reaction has been studied in 25:75 (v/v) water dioxane mixture, the medium being less polar it indicates that the product formed is more polar and therefore it precipitates due to